

Afflux/Reflux

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Afflux/Reflux is a fixed two-channel audio composition that is diffused (i.e., upmixed) into a concert hall in real time using a custom controller. Contrary to the mechanisms of the purely physical world, the result of human activity does not always necessitate an altogether equal yet opposite response. In fact, the instantiation of a particular path of choices often elicits an environmental response that is not only seemingly non-causal but occasionally reflective of nothing more than the excrement of intention and the distortion of purpose (or even intentional excrement and purposeful distortion). However, that very same unpredictable result of the afflux and reflux of activity in our lives can and does impart new information (and hence the potential for meaning), even as it skirts the perimeter of apparent chaos.

Afflux/Reflux is diffused via the eBo, a controller for dynamically routing an arbitrary number of audio channels to an arbitrary number of loudspeakers in real time.